

Supplemental Material

Supplemental Material for “AI-Powered Risk Analysis of Construction Contracts in P3 Projects”

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Text S1. Prompt designs used for AI-assisted risk analysis

Task 1

You are an expert contract analyst specializing in infrastructure P3/PPP agreements.

TASK: Analyze this Comprehensive Development Agreement. Identify any risk items. Find risk-related clause in the contract. Be comprehensive - include ALL material risks.

Return ONLY a valid JSON array. Format:

```
[
  {
    "risk_item": "Detailed description of the specific risk",
    "original_clause_text": "Exact text from contract (quote verbatim)",
    "clause_location": "Section X.X.X or Article X"
  }
]
```

Task 2

Task 2 tested four prompting strategies. All four prompts share the same role definition, risk taxonomy, label definitions, and output format. They differ only in the reasoning instructions inserted between the role definition and the output format.

Common preamble (shared across all four prompts).

You are an expert contract analyst specializing in infrastructure public-private partnership (P3/PPP) agreements.

Your task is to classify how each risk category is allocated in the provided contract. Use only the provided contract text.

Do not rely on general assumptions about P3 contracts.

Classify each risk allocation as exactly one of:

- Public: the public owner primarily bears the risk.
- Private: the private partner primarily bears the risk.

- Shared: both parties share the risk through cost sharing, deductibles, thresholds, caps, compensation, indexing, revenue sharing, or similar mechanisms.
- Silent / indeterminate: contract text does not clearly indicate.
- Not applicable: the risk does not apply to this contract.

Text S1.1 Basic zero-shot prompt

Provides the minimal instruction without reasoning steps or examples.

[Common preamble]

Risk category list: [31 categories]

Output ONLY a CSV table with NO header row and these columns:

Project, Prompt_Type, Risk_ID, Risk_Category, Allocation

CONTRACT TEXT: [document]

Text S1.2 Chain-of-thought prompt

Asks the model to reason in four steps before classifying.

[Common preamble]

For each risk category, think step by step:

Step 1 - Does the contract contain evidence or clauses related to this risk?

Step 2 - Which party bears primary responsibility, cost, delay, or liability?

Step 3 - Is there any sharing mechanism (compensation, caps, thresholds, indexing, relief events)?

Step 4 - Assign one final allocation.

Risk category list: [31 categories]

Output columns:

Project, Prompt_Type, Risk_ID, Risk_Category, Reasoning, Allocation

CONTRACT TEXT: [document]

Text S1.3 Few-shot prompt

Provides five worked examples covering all five label categories.

[Common preamble]

Use these examples as guidance:

Example 1 - Interest rates pre-financial close

Clause: Before financial close, changes in interest rates are borne by the public owner...

Allocation: Public

Example 2 - Changes by the Public Authority

Clause: The public agency must compensate the developer for scope, schedule, or specification changes...

Allocation: Public

Example 3 - Design

Clause: The developer is responsible for preparing, completing, and correcting the project design...

Allocation: Private

Example 4 - Site geology / conditions

Clause: The developer may request relief if unexpected subsurface conditions are encountered...

Allocation: Shared

Example 5 - Socio-political opposition

Clause: The provided contract text does not clearly state which party bears the risk...

Allocation: Silent / indeterminate

Risk category list: [31 categories]

CONTRACT TEXT: [document]

Text S1.4 Evidence-grounded prompt

Requires the model to locate and quote the relevant contract clause before classifying.

[Common preamble]

For each risk category, first identify and locate the relevant contract clause(s). Extract the specific clause evidence that supports the classification. Then classify the risk allocation based only on those clauses.

Risk category list: [31 categories]

Output columns:

Project, Prompt_Type, Risk_ID, Risk_Category, Clause_Location, Clause_Text, Allocation

Rules:

- Clause_Location: section or article number.
- Clause_Text: key verbatim phrase, max 200 chars.

CONTRACT TEXT: [document]

Tables S1–S2. Risk taxonomy and allocation labels

Tables S1–S2 define the 31 risk categories and the 5 allocation labels used in the LLM prompts and the expert annotation.

Table S1. Allocation labels and definitions.

Label	Definition
Public	The public owner (DOT, agency) primarily bears the risk.
Private	The private partner (developer, concessionaire, project company) primarily bears the risk.
Shared	Both parties share the risk through cost sharing, deductibles, thresholds, caps, compensation, indexing, or revenue sharing.
Silent / indeterminate	The contract text does not clearly indicate how the risk is allocated.
Not applicable	The risk does not apply to this contract or project context.

Table S2. Risk taxonomy: 31 categories used in the LLM prompts and expert annotation.

ID	Category	Description
1	Financing	Cost and availability of debt and equity financing.
2	Socio-political opposition and protesters	Public protests, opposition, or political resistance.
3	Change in law	Changes in applicable law, regulation, or tax.
4	Refinancing	Risks and gains from refinancing existing debt.
5	Inflation	Changes in price levels affecting costs.
6	Interest rates pre-financial close	Interest-rate movement before financing is locked.
7	Design	Errors, omissions, or changes in project design.
8	Right of way and easements	Land acquisition and easement risk.

9	Additional properties	Need for properties beyond initial scope.
10	Site geology / conditions	Unforeseen geological or subsurface conditions.
11	Environmental risks	Contamination, hazardous materials, environmental damage.
12	Archaeology, fossils, or protected species	Discoveries triggering work stoppage or remediation.
13	Access and adjustment to utilities	Utility relocation, access, and conflicts.
14	Permits	Obtaining and maintaining required permits.
15	Environmental permits	Specifically environmental permits and approvals.
16	Commodity price adjustments	Material and commodity price changes.
17	Changes by the Public Authority	Scope, schedule, or specification changes by the owner.
18	Revenue during construction	Revenue generation before service commencement.
19	Performance	Failure to meet performance standards.
20	Usage / demand risk	Traffic volume or demand below forecast.
21	Network modifications	Changes to surrounding network affecting the project.
22	Payment for services	Mechanism and timing of public payments.
23	Availability and service	Failure to maintain availability or service levels.
24	Operation expenses	Operating cost overruns.
25	Maintenance	Maintenance cost and quality risk.
26	Latent defects	Defects discovered after construction completion.
27	Transfer of ownership / contractual rights	Transfer or assignment of project rights.
28	Project Company default	Default by the SPV or concessionaire.
29	Termination by the Public	Termination for convenience or default by the owner.

Authority

30	Force majeure	Events beyond either party's control.
31	Residual value / handback	Asset condition at end of concession.

Table S3. Per-category observed agreement results

Table S3 presents the full per-category observed agreement (P_o) between Claude and the expert annotation, computed across all 14 P3 contracts (n = 14 comparisons per category, 434 total).

Table S3. Per-category observed agreement between Claude and expert annotation across 14 P3 contracts using the best-performing chain-of-thought prompt.

Rank	Risk category	Agreement (P_o)
1	Force majeure	100.0%
2	Residual value / handback	100.0%
3	Availability and service	100.0%
4	Performance	92.9%
5	Operation expenses	92.9%
6	Change in law	92.9%
7	Financing	92.9%
8	Design	85.7%
9	Maintenance	85.7%
10	Latent defects	78.6%
11	Environmental risks	78.6%
12	Usage / demand risk	78.6%
13	Access and adjustment to utilities	71.4%
14	Interest rates pre-financial close	64.3%
15	Network modifications	64.3%
16	Changes by the Public Authority	57.1%
17	Refinancing	57.1%
18	Additional properties	57.1%
19	Termination by the Public Authority	50.0%
20	Right of way and easements	50.0%

21	Transfer of ownership / contractual rights	50.0%
22	Archaeology, fossils, or protected species	42.9%
23	Commodity price adjustments	42.9%
24	Environmental permits	35.7%
25	Inflation	28.6%
26	Permits	28.6%
27	Site geology / conditions	21.4%
28	Payment for services	14.3%
29	Revenue during construction	14.3%
30	Socio-political opposition and protesters	7.1%
31	Project Company default	0.0%
